

1 **AN INTERLABORATORY COMPARISON ON WHOLE WATER SAMPLES**

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31 **ABSTRACT**

32 The European Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC requires monitoring of organic
33 priority pollutants in so-called whole water samples, i.e. in aqueous non-filtered samples
34 that contain natural colloidal and suspended particulate matter. Colloids and suspended
35 particles in the liquid phase constitute a challenge for sample homogeneity and stability.
36 Within the joint research project ENV08 “Traceable measurements for monitoring
37 critical pollutants under the European Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC”, whole
38 water test materials were developed by spiking defined amounts of aqueous slurries of
39 ultra-finely milled contaminated soil or sediment and aqueous solutions of humic acid
40 into a natural mineral water matrix. This paper presents the results of an European-wide
41 interlaboratory comparison (ILC) using this type of test materials. Target analytes were
42 tributyltin, polybrominated diphenyl ethers and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in the
43 ng/L concentration range. Results of the ILC indicate that the produced materials are
44 sufficiently homogeneous and stable to serve as samples for, e.g. proficiency testing or
45 method validation. To our knowledge, this is the first time that ready-to-use water
46 materials with a defined amount of suspended particulate and colloidal matter have been
47 applied as test samples in an interlaboratory exercise. These samples meet the
48 requirements of the European Water Framework Directive. Previous proficiency testing
49 schemes mainly employed filtered water samples fortified with a spike of the target
50 analyte in a water-miscible organic solvent.

51 **KEYWORDS**

52 Water Framework Directive, Interlaboratory comparison, Whole water sample,
53 Suspended particulate matter, Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, Polybrominated
54 diphenyl ethers, Tributyltin

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56 INTRODUCTION

57 The Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC [1] establishes a legal framework
58 for protecting the quality of surface and coastal waters in the European Union (EU). It
59 defines chemical substances for priority remediation and their Environmental Quality
60 Standards (EQSs) in Directive 2008/105/EC [2]. Two types of EQSs were set: annual
61 average concentrations (AA-EQS) for protection against long-term and chronic effects
62 and maximum allowable concentrations (MAC-EQS) to avoid serious irreversible
63 consequences for ecosystems due to acute exposure in the short term. EQSs for organic
64 pollutants refer to whole water samples, i.e. water with colloidal and suspended
65 particulate matter (SPM) which can pose an additional difficulty to analysis, particularly
66 of non-polar hydrophobic compounds that strongly adsorb to particles [3–5]. Therefore,
67 the WFD requires monitoring methods which allow the analysis of whole water samples.

68 All laboratories involved in the analysis and monitoring under the WFD should work
69 according to internationally accepted quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC)
70 schemes and should be obliged to demonstrate their competence by participating in
71 appropriate proficiency testing (PT) programmes on a regular basis [6, 7]. Several PT
72 schemes have been organized for WFD-regulated contaminants at EQS levels in aqueous
73 samples by, e.g. PT-WFD [7], the network of PT providers to support the implementation
74 of the WFD, IMEP [8, 9], the International Measurement Evaluation Programme of the
75 Institute for Reference Materials and Measurements (IRMM, Geel, Belgium) or within
76 the SWIFT-WFD project “Screening methods for water data information in support of
77 the implementation of the EU Water Framework Directive” [10]. However, these
78 interlaboratory comparisons (ILCs) mostly used filtered waters fortified with a spike of
79 the target analytes in a water-miscible organic solvent. An exception was the IMEP-23
80 ILC conducted in 2007/2008. Groundwater spiked with humic acid as a model for the

81 colloidal substances that are present in natural inland waters was used as matrix for the
82 eight WFD priority polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in this PT exercise [11].
83 However, the groundwater, humic acid solution and a PAH spike solution were supplied
84 to the participants as a kit. The final test samples had to be reconstituted by the IMEP-23
85 participants prior to analysis. To our knowledge, ready-to-use water test materials with a
86 defined amount of SPM and/or humic acid have not been applied for PT so far. Such
87 materials are not easy to produce because SPM and colloidal matter in the water phase
88 pose a particular challenge in terms of sample homogeneity and stability [12].

89 A feasibility study for the preparation of aqueous reference and test materials that contain
90 colloidal matter and SPM was performed as part of the joint research project ENV08
91 “Traceable measurements for monitoring critical pollutants under the European Water
92 Framework Directive 2000/60/EC” within the European Metrology Research
93 Programme [13]. The concepts developed for the preparation of the materials as well as
94 their homogeneity and stability assessment are described in detail elsewhere [14]. This
95 paper presents the results and conclusions of an European-wide ILC using the ENV08
96 whole water materials. To our knowledge, this is the first time that ready-to-use whole
97 water test materials were applied in an ILC. The ILC does not aim to test participants’
98 proficiency but the concepts for whole water reference materials developed in the project.
99 For this purpose, the key performance parameters of the ILC (reproducibility standard
100 deviation, repeatability standard deviation, recovery rates) were evaluated and discussed.
101 The samples meet the requirements of European water legislation since they contain not
102 only a liquid fraction but also a defined amount of SPM and colloidal matter. As in natural
103 surface waters, analytes are primarily bound to the SPM which makes extraction
104 challenging. Furthermore, the ultra-trace concentration level (ng/L) is a particular
105 challenge.

106 Recently, these types of water samples have also been used in a validation ILC for CEN
107 TC230 “water analysis” draft standards. Results of this CEN ILC will be published as
108 part of the standards and technical specification prEN 16691 Water quality—
109 Determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in whole water samples
110 using liquid–solid extraction combined with gas chromatography–mass spectrometry
111 (GC–MS), prEN 16694 Water quality—Determination of polybromodiphenyl ether
112 (PBDE) in whole water samples using solid-phase extraction (SPE) with SPE discs
113 combined with gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) and FprCEN/TS
114 16692 Water quality—Determination of tributyltin (TBT) in whole water samples using
115 solid-phase extraction (SPE) and gas chromatography with triple quadrupole mass
116 spectrometry. The technical specification has been published recently. The two standards
117 are currently under approval and will be released later in 2015. The new standards will
118 contribute to the harmonization of water monitoring in the EU.

119 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

120 **Test materials**

121 The ENV08 project focused on three groups of analytes listed as priority hazardous
122 substances in the WFD:

123 1. TBT cation

124 2. PBDEs (BDE28, BDE47, BDE99, BDE100, BDE153, BDE154)

125 3. PAHs [naphthalene (N), anthracene (A), fluoranthene (F), benzo(b)fluoranthene
126 (B(b)F), benzo(k)fluoranthene (B(k)F), benzo(a)pyrene (B(a)P), indeno(1,2,3,-cd)pyrene
127 (I), benzo(ghi)perylene (B(ghi)P)].

128 For each group of analytes, two types of samples were prepared: Sample 1 contained
129 humic acid and SPM and sample 2 contained only SPM. Test materials were prepared by

130 spiking defined amounts of aqueous slurries of ultra-finely milled contaminated soil or
131 sediment materials into brown glass bottles (VWR, Leuven, Belgium) pre-filled with 1 L
132 natural still mineral water “Reine” (Spa water, Spa, Belgium). The soil and sediment
133 raw materials used are listed in Table 1. Jet milling was carried out with an Alpine mill
134 (Alpine, Augsburg, Germany). The milled soil and sediment materials serve as model-
135 SPM in the water samples. Their top particle size was in the range from 9 μm to 12.5 μm ,
136 which corresponds to the average particle size of natural SPM in many respects [15].
137 ERM"-CZ 100 was used without further milling for the preparation of PAH-2 samples
138 since the particle size of this material was already in the desired range. The analytes are
139 strongly bound to the model-SPM and therefore mimic the situation in natural waters. No
140 spike of neat target analytes was added. Samples did not contain any organic solvent or
141 stabilizing agent. Additional to the SPM, an aqueous solution of commercial technical
142 grade humic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA) was added to some of the samples to
143 imitate natural colloids in the liquid phase. The dissolved organic carbon (DOC) of
144 these samples was about 5 mg/L, i.e. in the range that naturally occurs in surface waters.
145 In total, six different sample materials were prepared and distributed as listed in Table 1.
146 The analyte concentrations in the samples are defined by the distribution of the
147 compounds in the naturally contaminated SPM materials and therefore do not exactly
148 meet the EQS values. Concentrations in the milled SPM were determined by several
149 analytical methods [14].

150 From these data, the exact volume of the sample and the exact mass of SPM spiked, an
151 estimate of the analyte in the final aqueous test materials was calculated (estimated
152 concentrations in Table 1). For ERM"-CZ 100, the concentrations listed in the certificate
153 were used to calculate estimated concentrations in PAH sample 2. Estimated
154 concentrations were in the ng/L range, for PBDEs in sample 2 even considerably lower

155 than 1 ng/L. The relative expanded uncertainties of the estimated concentrations were
156 determined to be <25 % for all analytes in all samples. The uncertainty estimation is
157 described in a separate paper [16].

158 The homogeneity and short- and long-term stability of the samples were assessed [14].
159 For the homogeneity study, the amount of SPM added to a batch of samples was
160 controlled by placing a defined volume of the slurry in pre-weighed petri dishes. Two
161 petri dishes were filled before adding the slurry to the water samples, two in the middle
162 of the preparation sequence and two at the end. The dry mass of the loaded SPM was then
163 measured, and the relative standard deviation of the mean of the SPM aliquots was found
164 to be very small (between 0.18 % and 1.1 %). In addition, no trend in the sampled amount
165 with time was observed either. Therefore, it was concluded that the between-bottle
166 heterogeneity was sufficiently small. Sufficient proof of stability was gathered in a short-
167 term stability study for all samples kept at 4 #C in the dark for at least 4 weeks, i.e. long
168 enough for an ILC exercise. However, long-term stability of water samples is still an
169 unresolved issue. At tested conditions, gamma irradiation was found to be unsuitable for
170 conservation of prepared samples because of decomposition of analytes. More details on
171 the preparation procedures together with data for the characterization of the model-SPMs
172 and for the homogeneity and stability testing of the final aqueous test samples are given
173 in [14].

174 Furthermore, a systematic study of the interaction of the target analytes with different
175 container materials (amber glass, aluminium, fluorinated polyethylene FPE) has been
176 conducted in order to find the most suitable type of bottles. Strong adsorption of all target
177 analytes was observed on the container walls of FPE bottles, whereas aluminium and
178 glass turned out to be equally suited for PAHs and PBDEs. The volume of the container
179 had no significant impact on the loss of analytes due to adsorption. For TBT, bottles have

180 to be cleaned with acid; therefore, aluminium was unsuitable as container material.
181 Finally, amber glass bottles of 1 L capacity were selected for all three target analytes in
182 the ILC. The results of the container study are published in more detail in [17].

183 **Outline of the ILC**

184 The ILC was conducted within a period of about 6 weeks in June/July 2014. In total, 230
185 1 L samples were prepared, packed and finally dispatched from IRMM. Samples were
186 shipped immediately after preparation with overnight courier. Participants were
187 instructed to store them in the refrigerator at 4 °C after arrival. All samples were provided
188 in triplicate except PAH-2 which was provided in duplicate. Participants were requested
189 to shake the samples rigorously before extraction. The whole 1 L sample volume had to
190 be extracted at once, and subsampling was not allowed. At least one blank sample should
191 be analysed for each analyte group. It was recommended to use a natural mineral water
192 for the determination of blanks. Participants were asked to report blank values and details
193 of their analytical method.

194 Thirteen expert laboratories from eight European countries participated in the ILC
195 together with 11 institutions involved in the ENV08 project. The expert laboratories are
196 engaged in water monitoring under the WFD in their countries. ENV08 institutes are
197 mainly National Metrology Institutes and Designated Institutes. The ILC was fully
198 confidential. Participating laboratories were denoted with a code as, for instance, Lab 1.
199 A list of all participants in alphabetical order is given in the electronic supplementary
200 material (ESM), Table S1. Laboratories could opt to choose one or several of the three
201 analytes TBT, PBDE and PAH. In total, ten data sets each were returned for TBT (five
202 from expert laboratories and five from ENV08 institutes) and PBDEs (four from expert
203 laboratories and six from ENV08 institutes). Twelve data sets were received for PAHs
204 (eight from expert laboratories and four from ENV08 institutes).

205 **Analytical methods**

206 Participants could use a method of their choice. However, both the liquid and the
207 particulate matter phase should be included in the analysis. All methods are listed in Table
208 2 and in more detail in the ESM, Tables S2 to S4. All participants except Lab 18 (TBT
209 samples only) extracted the liquid and particulate matter phase together within one
210 step. Lab 18 filtered the TBT samples and analysed the liquid and SPM phases separately.

211 **Statistical analysis**

212 Statistical analysis of the ILC results was performed according to ISO 5725-5:2002 [18]
213 using the QuoData PROLab™ software for interlaboratory tests [19]. A robust approach
214 (algorithms A and S) was applied to calculate the mean and standard deviations, i.e.
215 outlier suspected values were not excluded. Algorithms A and S are described in
216 detail in Section 6 of [18]: robust methods for data analysis.

217 **RESULTS**

218 As an example for each group of analytes, Figs. 1, 2 and 3 display the results of the ILC
219 for TBT in sample 2, BDE47 in sample 1 and benzo(ghi)perylene in sample 2. Data for
220 all other analytes/samples are included in the ESM Figures S1 to S27. Table 3 summarizes
221 the key ILC performance parameters obtained from the statistical analysis. Recoveries in
222 Table 3 were calculated relative to the estimated values in Table 1.

223 **DISCUSSION**

224 **Reproducibility and repeatability standard deviations, recovery rates**

225 The reproducibility standard deviation is a measure of the variability between test results
226 obtained in different laboratories, whereas the repeatability standard deviation concerns
227 the variability between independent test results obtained within a single laboratory. In
228 general, a small reproducibility and repeatability standard deviation and a good agreement

229 of the mean of participants' results with the estimated concentration indicate that the test
230 materials are eligible, i.e. sufficiently homogeneous and stable. For 24 out of the 30
231 analyte/sample combinations, the relative reproducibility standard deviation $C_{V,R}$ was
232 found to be <60 %. With one exception (anthracene in sample 2), the relative repeatability
233 standard deviation $C_{V,r}$ was found to be <15 %, and recovery rates g were between 70 %
234 and 130 % for 22 out of the 30 analyte/sample combination (Table 3). As a further check
235 for the suitability of the test samples, the mean of participants' results was compared with
236 the estimated concentrations in sample 2 (Fig. 4) and sample 1 (Figure S31 in the ESM).
237 The agreement is good for 24 out of the 30 analyte/sample combinations. The estimated
238 value is within the $(\text{mean} \pm 2C_{V,R})$ interval (dashed lines in Figs. 1, 2, 3) for all
239 analytes/samples except TBT in sample 1 and fluoranthene in both samples. Taking into
240 account the complexity of the test samples, the low concentrations, the variety of
241 analytical methods and the relative low number of data sets, these performance data are
242 acceptable.

243 The relatively small repeatability standard deviation of <15 % furthermore confirms that
244 the samples were sufficiently homogeneous for the purpose of this study, thereby
245 confirming the findings available at the time of preparation of the test samples.

246 The ILC was conducted within a period of about 6 weeks. For none of the analytes, a
247 dependency of the measured values on the date of extraction was observed. Results
248 scatter, but there is no trend towards lower values with time as it is shown in Fig. 5 for
249 benzo(b)fluoranthene in sample 1. This is a further verification of a sufficient short-term
250 stability of the whole water samples, thereby confirming the findings available at the time
251 of preparation of the test samples.

252 In general, there seems to be a tendency towards lower recovery rates with higher analyte
253 concentration. Fluoranthene, for instance, is the analyte with the highest estimated

254 concentration and the one with the lowest recovery (34 %) in both samples. This trend is
255 somewhat surprising, and currently no satisfactory explanation can be given. The
256 physico-chemical interactions taking place when adding model-SPM to pre-filled water
257 bottles are not known in detail. They may depend on the bottle material, the concentration,
258 polarity and solubility of the analyte as well as pH, ionic strength and other properties of
259 the water phase [20]. Lab 18 performed a series of TBT measurements with freshly
260 prepared whole water samples containing SPM. Recovery rates were found to be
261 significantly higher (112 % with an expanded uncertainty (95 % confidence interval) of
262 11 %, six replicate measurements) compared with the ones in the ILC (66 %). This finding
263 indicates that the concentration or distribution of TBT in the whole water sample changes
264 to some extent within a very short time after addition of the SPM. Afterwards, the samples
265 remain sufficiently stable for at least the course of the ILC, i.e. a few weeks. Results of a
266 short-term stability study [14] verify the latter.

267 The presence of humic acid in sample 1 led to slightly lower recovery rates, particularly
268 for the five- and six-ring PAHs, and slightly higher standard deviations for PAHs and
269 PBDEs. The humic acid apparently hampers extraction of the analytes and phase
270 separation in the liquid/liquid extraction (LLE) process.

271 **Dependence of ILC results on the analytical methods**

272 *TBT*

273 For TBT, two different detection methods were applied: (1) GC-MS or GC-MS/MS and
274 (2) GC-ICP-MS, the latter often in combination with isotope dilution calibration using
275 ¹¹⁹Sn-enriched TBT. GC-ICP-MS results were found to be higher compared with GC-
276 MS-based results (Fig. 6) which, probably, can be explained by the higher sensitivity of
277 ICP-MS. The majority of participants applied LLE, one participant (Lab 5) used SPE,

278 one participant (Lab 9) used headspace solid-phase microextraction, and one participant
279 (Lab 18) analysed the liquid phase by LLE and separately the filtered solid phase by
280 ultrasonication. All these extraction methods appear to be equivalent.

281 *PBDEs*

282 For the PBDEs, no systematic difference was observed between the results obtained by
283 LLE and SPE as shown for BDE99, sample 1, in Figure S28 in the ESM. Furthermore,
284 different detection/calibration modes (GC–EI–MS-based methods with ¹³C-labelled
285 internal standards, GC–NCI–MS-based methods with fluorinated or ¹³C-labelled internal
286 standards, GC–ICP–MS with isotope dilution calibration using ⁸¹Br-labelled PBDEs) did
287 not lead to systematic differences in the results (Figure S29 in the ESM).

288 *PAHs*

289 There was no difference observed in the results obtained by LLE and SPE (Figure S30 in
290 the ESM). For detection and quantification, GC–MS-based methods were used by all, but
291 one participant (Lab 17) who applied liquid chromatography coupled to an atmospheric
292 pressure photoionization source (LC–APPI–MS/MS).

293 **CONCLUSION**

294 For the first time, an ILC was conducted with whole water test materials which contained
295 defined amounts of SPM and organic colloidal matter and therefore mimicked the
296 composition of natural surface waters. The concentration of the target analytes TBT,
297 PBDEs and PAHs was in the ng/L range, i.e. in the range of EQS set by the WFD.
298 Analytes were strongly bound to the suspended particle phase as in natural surface waters.
299 Performance parameters of the ILC such as recovery rates and reproducibility and
300 repeatability standard deviations indicate that the test materials prepared were indeed

301 suitable, i.e. sufficiently homogeneous and stable for, e.g. proficiency testing or method
302 validation. For the majority of analytes, the robust mean of the participants' results agreed
303 well with the estimated concentration in the samples, calculated from the concentration
304 in the SPM and the mass of SPM added. Altogether, the results of the ILC confirm that it
305 is possible to prepare whole water reference materials by precisely spiking of aqueous
306 slurries of ultra-finely milled particles into a water matrix. This is a step forward to the
307 production of realistic whole water test and reference materials which meet the
308 requirements of European water legislation.

309 ILC participants applied different analytical procedures. For TBT, the results of GC–ICP–
310 MS in combination with isotope dilution calibration were closer to the estimated values
311 than GC–MS-based results. For PBDEs and PAHs, the results obtained with different
312 extraction and/or separation and detection techniques did not vary significantly.

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TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1 Composition of the test samples and annual average Environmental Quality Standards (AA-EQSs) for the target analytes; abbreviations for the analytes are given in section Test materials

Sample	Humic acid concentration (DOC) in the whole water sample [mg/L]	SPM raw material	SPM concentration in the whole water sample [mg/L]	Estimated analyte concentration in the whole water sample ^a [ng/L]	AA-EQS [2] [ng/L]
TBT-1	5	BCR 646 organotin compounds in river sediment	8.2	TBT: 4.07	TBT: 0.2
TBT-2	0	BCR 646 + TBT blank sediment ^b	Total: 21.1 BCR 646: 8.2 Blank SPM: 12.9	TBT: 4.07	TBT: 0.2
PBDE- 1	5	Freshwater sediment, IRMM candidate reference material	193.5	BDE 28: 0.032 BDE 47: 2.54 BDE 99: 5.90 BDE 100: 0.88 BDE 153: 1.20	Σ 6 PBDEs: 0.5

				BDE 153: 0.56	
PBDE- 2	0	Freshwater sediment, IRMM candidate reference material	25.2	BDE 28: 0.004 BDE 47: 0.33 BDE 99: 0.77 BDE 100: 0.11 BDE 153: 0.16 BDE 153: 0.07	Σ 6 PBDEs: 0.5
PAH-1	5	Industrial soil, BAM PT material	38.6	N: 46 A: 20.6 F: 367 B(b)F: 120 B(k)F: 89 B(a)P: 90 I: 101 B(ghi)P: 118	N: 2400 A: 100 F: 100 B(b)F+B(k)F: 30 B(a)P: 50 I + B(ghi)P: 2

PAH-2	0	ERM®-CZ 100 PAH in fine dust	20.2	N: - A: 5.7 F: 94.5 B(b)F: 28.7 B(k)F: 13.5 B(a)P: 14.6 I: 21.4 B(ghi)P: 35.6	N: 2400 A: 100 F: 100 B(b)F+B(k)F: 30 B(a)P: 50 I + B(ghi)P: 2
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DOC: dissolved organic carbon

^a calculated from the analyte concentration determined in the milled SPM and the mass of SPM spiked

^b Blank sediment obtained by jet-milling of ERM®-CC141 (calcareous loam soil) to a top particle size of 10 µm; with TBT concentration < detection limit of method used.

Table 2 Analytical methods applied in the ILC

	TBT	PBDE	PAH
Derivatisation	Ethylation with NaBEt ₄	-	-
Extraction	Liquid/liquid extraction (LLE) with hexane or isooctane; solid phase extraction (SPE) with speediscs; headspace solid phase microextraction (HS-SPME) ; ultrasonic extraction of the SPM	LLE with hexane, isooctane or dichloromethane; speedisk SPE	LLE with dichloromethane, petrolether or hexane; speedisk SPE
Clean-up of extract	None; Al ₂ O ₃ column	None; multi-layer silica column; H ₂ SO ₄	None; silica column; drying with Na ₂ SO ₄ or Gore-Tex membrane
Separation/detection	GC-MS; GC-MS/MS; GC-ICP-MS	GC-MS or –MS/MS with electron impact or negative chemical ionization; GC-HR-MS; GC-ICP-MS	GC-MS; GC-MS/MS; LC-APPI-MS/MS
Calibration	Species specific isotope dilution (ID) with ¹¹⁹ Sn enriched TBT; calibration curve with deuterated TBT or tripropyltin as internal standard	Species specific ID with Br labeled isotopes; calibration curve with ¹³ C BDEs or fluorinated analogues	Calibration curve without internal standard or deuterated or ¹³ C labeled internal standards

Table 3 Key performance parameters of the ILC; abbreviations for the analytes are given in section *Test materials*

Analyte	Sample 1 (with humic acid)					Sample 2 (without humic acid)				
	<i>n</i>	\bar{x} ng/L	η %	$C_{V,R}$ %	$C_{V,r}$ %	<i>n</i>	\bar{x} ng/L	η %	$C_{V,R}$ %	$C_{V,r}$ %
TBT	10	2.66	65	21	6.4	10	2.69	66	29	5,8
BDE 28	8	0.05	155	82	7.9	6	0.009	225	72	12
BDE 47	10	2.65	104	30	5.7	10	0.41	125	24	13
BDE 99	10	6.35	108	40	6.9	10	0.78	102	38	12
BDE 100	10	1.11	127	54	10	9	0.15	135	36	9.0
BDE 153	10	1.13	94	57	11	9	0.15	97	30	5.9
BDE 154	10	0.61	109	46	11	8	0.08	107	27	7.0
N	9	32.2	70	79	14	9	21.6	*	117	11
A	10	20.3	98	66	9.9	10	4.0	70	54	32
F	11	125	34	50	7.3	11	32.3	34	55	9.5
B(b)F	11	91.7	76	44	6.8	11	26.7	93	41	4.9
B(k)F	11	49.7	56	52	6.4	11	11.6	86	47	5.8
B(a)P	12	67.8	75	45	8.3	12	13.5	93	47	6.4

I	11	82.0	82	56	11	11	20.9	97	35	8.2
B(ghi)P	12	80.9	70	63	12	12	25.9	73	22	8.2

n : number of data sets, $C_{V,R}$: coefficient of variation of reproducibility, \bar{x} : robust mean, $C_{V,r}$: coefficient of variation of repeatability, η : recovery rate, calculated relative to the estimated values in Table 1

*: Naphthalene was not certified in the raw SPM used, therefore no estimated value and recovery rate could be calculated

- 1 **Fig. 1** ILC results for TBT, sample 2, estimated concentration 4.1 ng/L (dotted line);
- 2 solid line: robust mean, dashed lines: robust mean $\pm 2C_{V,R}$ (reproducibility standard
- 3 deviation); \diamond bottle 1, \square bottle 2, \triangle bottle 3

4

5

6 **Fig. 2** ILC results for BDE47, sample 1, estimated concentration 2.5 ng/L (dotted line);
7 solid line: robust mean, dashed lines: robust mean $\pm 2C_{V,R}$ (reproducibility standard
8 deviation); \diamond bottle 1, \square bottle 2, \triangle bottle 3

9

10

11 **Fig. 3** ILC results for benzo(ghi)perylene, sample 2, estimated concentration 36 ng/L
12 (dotted line); solid line: robust mean, dashed lines: robust mean $\pm 2C_{V,R}$
13 (reproducibility standard deviation); \diamond bottle 1, \square bottle 2, \triangle bottle 3

14

15

16 **Fig. 4** Comparison of the robust mean of participants' results with the estimated
17 concentration, sample 1; error bars reproducibility standard deviation $C_{V,R}$. Note that
18 the y-axis and error bars are in logarithmic scale to display all analytes within one graph

19

20

21 **Fig. 5** ILC results for benzo(b)fluoranthene, sample 1, as a function of the extraction
22 date; solid line: robust mean, dashed lines: robust mean ± 2.9 reproducibility standard
23 deviation $C_{V,R}$; \diamond bottle 1, \square bottle 2, \triangle bottle 3

24

25

26 **Fig. 6** ILC results for TBT, sample 2, influence of the detection/calibration method;
 27 solid line: robust mean, dashed lines: robust mean $\pm 2C_{V,R}$ (reproducibility standard
 28 deviation); dotted line: estimated concentration, \diamond bottle 1, \square bottle 2, \triangle bottle 3,
 29 unfilled symbols GC-MS-based results, no isotope dilution, dark grey symbols GC-
 30 MS/MS with isotope dilution, black symbols GC-ICP-MS with isotope dilution, light
 31 grey symbols GC-ICP-MS, internal standard tripropyltin

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